

Juvenile Salmon Migration Observations from the Hakai Institute Juvenile Salmon Program in the Discovery Islands in British Columbia, Canada in 2021

by

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Abstract

The Hakai Institute Juvenile Salmon Program has been monitoring juvenile salmon migrations in the Discovery Islands in British Columbia, Canada since 2015 with the specific purpose to understand how ocean conditions experienced by juvenile salmon during their early marine migration impact their growth, health, and ultimately survival. This report summarizes migration timing, purse-seine catch abundance and composition, fish lengths and weights, sea-louse loads, and ocean temperatures observed from 7 years of this research and monitoring program. Sockeye migration timing was 11 days later than normal in 2021 occurring on June 8, the latest observed in the time series. Peak chum migration timing was similar to previous years occurring on June 14. Catch intensity of sockeye was the lowest on record in the time series. Pink were observed in low numbers given the off-cycle year for juvenile outmigrants from the Fraser River. Chum catches were close to their time-series average. Chum salmon dominated catch proportions followed by pink, sockeye, herring, and coho. Mean annual fork length for sockeye was not different than the time series average, though pink and chum salmon were shorter than average. The abundance of motile *Lepeophtheirus salmonis* and *Caligus clemensi* sea lice on sockeye, pink, and chum were within their normal time series ranges in 2021. May–June 30 m depth integrated ocean temperature in the northern Strait of Georgia in 2021 was 0.14 °C colder than average for the time series.

Introduction

The first months after marine entry are a critical period for juvenile salmon growth (Beamish and Mahnken 2001), which may ultimately be responsible for interannual variability and long-term declines in British Columbian salmon stocks (Peterman et al. 2010; Beamish et al. 2012). Two of the probable causes of these declines are the impacts of climate change on marine food web dynamics and the population level effects of pathogens and predators (Cohen 2012). The Discovery Islands and Johnstone Strait are regions of reduced food availability for migrating juvenile salmon (James et al. 2020) and may present a trophic challenge for fish emigrating from the Strait of Georgia (McKinnell et al. 2014). This region has also historically been one of high densities of salmon aquaculture.

The Hakai Institute Juvenile Salmon Program has been monitoring juvenile salmon migrations in the Discovery Islands (Figure 1) since 2015 to determine the factors that influence the health and early marine survival of sockeye (*Oncorhynchus nerka*), pink (*O. gorbuscha*), and chum (*O. keta*) salmon (Hunt et al. 2018). This report summarizes migration timing, fish length, and parasite loads of sockeye, pink and chum salmon observed in 2021 and compares these metrics to observations made between 2015 and 2020. In addition, we present data on relative abundance of all salmonid species sampled and Pacific herring, and ocean temperature.

Migration timing, which reflects a combination of marine entry date and Strait of Georgia residence time, interacts with plankton phenology to determine the foraging conditions experienced by juvenile salmon in the Strait of Georgia and Discovery Islands. The condition of salmon when they reach the Discovery Islands is expected to reflect the environmental

conditions experienced during their passage through the Strait of Georgia, and their preparedness to traverse the poor foraging environment of Johnstone Strait. We assess the interannual variability of juvenile sockeye, pink, chum, coho, and herring population characteristics in conjunction with the ocean conditions fish experienced in the Strait of Georgia and Discovery Islands from 2015 to 2021. These measures provide essential support information for ongoing research into the growth, survival, and the impact of ocean conditions experienced by salmon during their early marine migration through this critical region.

Figure 1. Juvenile salmon and oceanography sampling stations in the Discovery Islands in 2021.

Methods

Field methods

Juvenile salmon were targeted during their northward migration from the Strait of Georgia through the Discovery Islands, near north-eastern Vancouver Island, British Columbia. Since 2015, fish were sampled from May to July each year, on a weekly basis, from the Discovery Islands. Sampling occurred in nearshore marine habitats, where depth was > 10 m and distance from shore was typically less than 300 m, using hand-operated purse seine nets (bunt:

27 m x 9 m with 13 mm mesh; tow: 46 m x 9 m with 76 mm mesh) (Groot et al. 1985; Godwin et al. 2015). This method effectively catches sockeye, pink and chum, and incidentally captures coho (*O. kisutch*), chinook (*O. tshawytschya*), and Pacific herring (*Clupea pallasii*). Surveys were conducted prior to the arrival of sockeye in early May and until sockeye were no longer caught, usually in early July. All animal interactions complied with Canadian Council on Animal Care permit A16-0101. Temperature data were also collected weekly by deploying a Maestro conductivity, temperature, and depth profiler CTD (RBR Ltd., Ottawa, Canada) to depths >30 m at station QU39 (Figure 1) in the northern Strait of Georgia. Hunt et al. (2018) provides a detailed description of the field sampling methodology.

Data analysis

This report highlights variability for key ecosystem and stock assessment variables in relation to the averages from 2015–2020 to characterize interannual variation. Only data from sites that were sampled across all years were used for calculations. Analyses were conducted using R v4.0.5 (R Core Team 2022). The original study intent had a focus on capturing sockeye and studying their ecology with co-migrating pink and chum; thus in 2015 and 2016, pink and chum were only enumerated when sockeye were also caught. Starting in 2017, the program transitioned to enumerating pink, chum, and other species, even when sockeye were absent. Therefore, to make observations consistent among years, migration timing, catch intensity, and catch proportions for sockeye, pink, and chum were calculated based only on seines that caught sockeye.

Peak migration date was estimated using the median date of cumulative catch abundance for each species in the Discovery Islands. This metric was favoured over a “catch per unit effort” approach because of the sampling design. Cumulative abundance was calculated over the period May 1–July 9, providing a consistent period for interannual comparisons of migration timing. This time period begins prior to sockeye salmon arrival in the region and ends after their departure. Furthermore, as adult pink salmon run sizes have historically been even-year dominant in the Fraser River, we don’t expect to catch many out-migrating juvenile pinks in odd years (Heard 1991). Consequently, only even years were included in the calculation of pink migration time-series averages.

Catch intensity was calculated to provide a measure of interannual relative-abundance for sockeye, pink, and chum. Catch intensity was defined as the average number of individuals of species *i* when $i > 0$ and when sockeye were also caught. In effect, catch intensity summarizes the abundance of each species in a community of co-migrating sockeye, pink, and chum salmon. Species specific catch proportion was calculated by dividing the number of each species caught in each year by the sum of all fish caught in that year. For sockeye, pink, and chum, differences between fork lengths observed in the most recent year compared to the time-series average were calculated using Welch’s two sample t-test.

Mean abundance estimates and 95% confidence intervals of *C. clemensi* and *L. salmonis* sea lice were bootstrapped 1,000 times from the counts of lice obtained for each species of louse, respecting the hierarchical nature of sampling on sockeye, pink, and chum from within the same seine. Only motile (i.e., pre-adult and adult) stages were included in analyses because the

juvenile life stages (i.e., copepodid and chalmus) were not enumerated every year. Sea lice were removed, counted, and identified in the laboratory using a dissecting microscope.

Depth-integrated temperature from the top 30 m of the water column at station QU39 (Figure 1) were compared for May and June, when most juvenile salmon migrate through the region. The 30 m integrated depth was chosen because juvenile salmon generally inhabit surface waters (Levings and Kotyk 1983, Beamish 2012). To visualize temperature anomalies throughout the entire spring, a local polynomial regression function from the R ‘stats’ package called ‘loess’ (Cleveland et al. 1992; R Core Team 2022) was applied to ocean temperatures from all years except the most recent, to represent the average seasonal temperature trend to which we compared the current year observations.

To characterize the interannual variability of each key migration variable, standard z-scores were calculated. Z scores assume that the variable being standardized has a normal distribution, so each set of annual observations was first tested for normality using the Shapiro-Wilk test. Where the assumption of normality was not met, variables were transformed to ranks and then normalized using an inverse normal transformation to calculate a non-parametric z-score (Blom 1958). These z-scores were then visualized in an anomaly heatmap.

Results

The peak migration date for sockeye in the Discovery Islands in 2021 was on June 8th, 11 days later than the time series average of May 28 (Figure 2). The peak migration date for chum was on June 14, 2 days earlier than the average of June 16. Catch intensity for sockeye salmon was 21 which is the lowest of the time series (Figure 3). Pink catch intensity was 71 and for chum salmon catch intensity was 190. Catch proportion was dominated by chum with 68.7% of the catch followed by pink salmon at 22.7% while sockeye salmon were just 7.7% of the total annual catch (Figure 4).

Sockeye average fork length in 2021 was 106.7 mm which when compared to the time series average of 108.2 mm results in a statistically insignificant difference of -1.5 mm ($p = 0.28$, 95% CI -4.3 – 1.2 mm). Average pink fork length in 2021 was 88.3 mm which compared to the time series average of 96.3 mm results in a statistically significant difference of -8 mm ($p < 0.000$, 95% CI -10.5 – -5.5 mm). Average chum fork length in 2021 was 99.1 mm which compared to the time series average of 106.3 mm results in a statistically significant difference of -7.2 mm ($p < 0.000$, 95% CI -10.2 – -4.1 mm). Fork length-weight regressions indicate that fish condition was within the normal range in 2021 (Figure 6).

The abundance of motile sea lice on juvenile salmon in the Discovery Islands was variable between species of salmon and louse in 2021 (Figure 7). Sockeye salmon had an average of 0.37 *C. clemensi* per fish and 0.04 *L. salmonis* per fish. Chum salmon had 0.51 *C. clemensi* per fish and 0.02 *L. salmonis* per fish. Pink salmon had 0.48 *C. clemensi* per fish, and 0.01 *L. salmonis* per fish.

Ocean temperature in the top 30 m of the water column in May and June during the juvenile salmon out-migration at QU39 in the northern Strait of Georgia was 11.4 °C, 0.14 colder °C than average (Table 3).

Figure 2. Cumulative catch of sockeye, pink, and chum in the Discovery Islands between 2015 and 2020 compared to 2021 migration timing.

Figure 3. The catch intensity (average number of individuals of species *i* when *i* > 0 and when sockeye were also caught) of sockeye, pink, and chum salmon in the Discovery Islands.

Numbers under each bar indicate the number of seines in which the species was caught, and error bars indicate 1 standard error.

Figure 4. The annual proportion of fish captured in the Discovery Islands.

Figure 5. Distributions of juvenile salmon fork lengths for each year in the Discovery Islands. Note that these distributions contain multiple age classes.

Figure 6. Fork length-weight regressions for juvenile salmon caught in the Discovery Islands in 2021 coloured red, compared to time series (2015–2020) in black.

Figure 7. The abundance of motile sea lice on juvenile salmon in the Discovery Islands. The error bars indicate the 95 % confidence region.

Figure 8. Thirty-meter depth-integrated ocean temperatures at station QU39 in the northern Strait of Georgia. The solid black line represents average temperatures from 2015–2020. Blue areas represent temperatures from 2021 that are below the 2015–2020 average and red areas represent above average temperatures.

Figure 9. The number of standard deviations (z score) from the time-series average (2015-2021) for key migration parameters of juvenile salmon from the Discovery Islands. Size and colour saturation of circles indicates the magnitude of the deviation. Blue colour indicates less than average; grey indicates average; red indicates greater than average. Peak migration date is based on the median date of fish capture. Fork length is the average fork length. Sea-louse abundance is the average abundance of all sea-louse species in their motile life stage. Ocean temperature describes the mean ocean temperature in the top 30 m at station QU39 in the northern Strait of Georgia in May and June.

Discussion

Sockeye migration timing in 2021 was the latest in the time series. Interestingly, the second latest migration date in this time series was observed in 2017 which is the same genetic cohort observed in 2021 due to the four-year life cycle of most sockeye salmon and the resulting cyclic dominance of Fraser River sockeye stocks (Ricker 1997). Sockeye catch intensity in 2021 was also the lowest observed in the time series and the second lowest catch also occurred in the same genetic cohort from 2017. The sockeye that out-migrated in 2021 are the brood from the 2019 adult return which had only 571,000 sockeye return to freshwater, a new record low in

abundance of adult sockeye returns to the Fraser River (PSC, 2020). The 2019 sockeye return was further impacted by the Big Bar Landslide on the Fraser River mainstem near Boston Bar, BC that blocked access to between 60-100% of sockeye stocks that spawn above where the landslide occurred. It's no surprise then that 2021 had the fewest number of juvenile out-migrating sockeye in our time series going back to 2015.

Sea-lice loads were within the normal range of our time-series despite only 6 fish farms being stocked in the Discovery Islands during the sockeye outmigration period when normally there are between 9 and 13 active farms (DFO, 2021). The connection between salmon farm stocking status and sea-lice loads described in this report should be interpreted with caution because this study only looked for motile adult stages of sea-lice which are more likely to have originated from the Strait of Georgia (Brookson et al. 2020) rather than from farms in the Discovery Islands.

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Data

Data are open-access under the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) license. Reuse of the data requires attribution to the data providers in the form of a dataset citation, though offers of collaboration are preferred. Program data, metadata and a recommended citation can be found at <http://doi.org/10.21966/1.566666>.

Tables

Table 1. Migration timing statistics for the cumulative catch of sockeye, pink, and chum salmon in the Discovery Islands in 2021, compared to the time-series average (2015 - 2020). Q1 is when 25 % of the species passed through the regions, peak date is the median when 50 % passed through, Q3 is 75 %, and Spread is the difference between Peak Date and Q1.

Year	Region	Species	Q1	Peak Date	Q3	Spread
2015 - 2021	DI	Chum	June 07	June 16	June 24	9
2015 - 2021	DI	Pink	June 05	June 16	June 16	11
2015 - 2021	DI	Sockeye	May 26	May 28	June 04	1
2021	DI	Chum	June 04	June 14	June 21	10
2021	DI	Sockeye	June 04	June 08	June 14	4

Table 2. Mean fork lengths (mm) for each year, species, and region with the 95 % confidence interval (CI). The column N indicates the number of fish measured.

Year	Species	N	Fork Length	CI
2015	Sockeye	479	109.0	1.0
2015	Pink	65	110.4	4.3
2015	Chum	184	113.4	2.4
2016	Sockeye	649	96.9	0.8
2016	Pink	173	98.6	2.3
2016	Chum	183	99.7	2.4
2017	Sockeye	269	121.0	2.0
2017	Pink	28	92.6	6.4
2017	Chum	112	105.9	2.5
2018	Sockeye	192	114.7	2.4
2018	Pink	206	87.8	1.7
2018	Chum	191	97.7	2.2
2019	Sockeye	372	114.5	0.9
2019	Pink	142	99.5	2.8
2019	Chum	200	114.2	2.4
2020	Sockeye	170	107.8	1.6
2020	Pink	102	96.8	3.0
2020	Chum	66	106.0	3.4
2021	Sockeye	106	106.7	2.7
2021	Pink	97	88.3	2.2
2021	Chum	106	99.1	2.9

Table 3. Mean 30 m depth-integrated ocean temperatures from May and June at station QU39 in the northern Strait of Georgia from 2015-2021

Year	Temperature (C)	SD
2015	11.23	0.98
2016	11.72	1.02
2017	11.24	1.07
2018	11.89	1.06
2019	11.05	1.04
2020	12.30	1.09
2021	11.38	1.33

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